

Challenges In Blended Learning Implementation: Mathematics Teachers in Focus

Daisy N. Obera

Abstract. This qualitative phenomenological study investigated the lived experiences of ten junior high school mathematics teachers from public secondary schools in the Nabunturan East District, Davao de Oro Division, in relation to their challenges and coping strategies in implementing blended learning. The study aimed to capture the essence of their experiences amid the new normal educational landscape. Data were gathered through in-depth interviews and a focus group discussion, and analyzed using thematic content analysis. Three major themes emerged from the data: technological access and limitations, learner motivation and participation, and teacher preparedness and workload. Teachers identified significant obstacles, including inconsistent internet access, inadequate digital resources, and unequal access to resources among learners. Student motivation and engagement fluctuated, as learners struggled with self-directed study and navigating modular and online platforms. Furthermore, teachers experienced increased workload and emotional strain due to the need for constant lesson adaptation. Despite these challenges, participants showed resilience and adaptability, promoting collegial collaboration and exploring innovative approaches to enhance student engagement. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of the significant demands placed on educators in blended learning contexts and offers recommendations for enhancing educational policy and teacher support systems.

KEY WORDS

1. Blended learning 2. phenomenological study 3. mathematics education

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1. Introduction

Implementing blended learning poses several challenges for mathematics teachers. Balancing face-to-face instruction with modular components and integrating self-learning modules into teaching-learning processes can be overwhelming, requiring teachers to possess not only pedagogical expertise but also methodological proficiency. Also, assessing learners' understanding and engagement in a blended setup can be more complex compared to traditional methods, necessitating innovative assessment strategies, and maintaining learners' motivation and managing their time effectively in a blended learning scenario. These factors collectively create a demanding environment for mathematics teachers striving to implement blended learning successfully. In the United States, particularly in Houston, Texas, K-12 institutions are embracing the shift toward blended learning by equipping schools with technology and tools that sup-

port authentic learning experiences. School superintendents across the region are actively integrating blended learning strategies to enhance student achievement and deliver high-quality instruction. Blended learning serves as a bridge between social media platforms and electronic classroom management systems (Jamon, 2021). In Germany, the reasons behind learners' decisions to drop out of a blended learning course were uncovered, revealing several critical issues. Learners cited a lack of support and poor coordination between the face-to-face and computer-assisted components as major concerns (Stracke, 2019). Additionally, dissatisfaction with the absence of printed materials and resistance to using computers for language learning further contributed to their disengagement, highlighting persistent gaps in blended learning design and implementation. In Saudi Arabia, providing a learning environment enriched with digital technology tools has been shown to help learners stay engaged in their activities while recognizing the significance of educational technologies in their academic journey. To build an educational system where both learners and parents feel more connected with schools, it is essential to go beyond the traditional boundaries of school calendars, age-based grade levels, and geographical limitations. As emphasized, implementing blended learning in such contexts can foster stronger connections and contribute to a more inclusive and effective learning environment (Abdalahdi 2019). As the Department of Education faces the challenges to continually provide a quality education for all despite the challenges in our educational system, public schools and even some private schools chose the blended learning as their learning modality of which is a learning delivery that combines face-to-face with any, or a mix of, modular distance learning, online distance learning, and television/radio-based instruction. This is so because blended learning system is one of the answers to individualized instruction focuses

on the needs of the individual learner. On the other hand, other learners using the same teaching method can skip topics they already know and go on to advanced information (Gilmour, 2020). In the Philippines context, particularly in Nueva Ecija, despite the potential of blended learning to enhance learners' comprehension and improve teaching practices, many teachers continue to struggle with its effective implementation, particularly in the use of self-learning modules. This challenge is evident in various schools where educators face barriers in fully embracing the blended learning model. While some studies report positive outcomes, findings remain mixed, and there is a noticeable lack of in-depth research focusing on the specific challenges encountered during implementation. Notably, limited attention has been given to the lived experiences of mathematics teachers. (Moran, 2020). In the Philippines, particularly at Laguna City, Yazon (2020) explored the firsthand experiences of teachers in implementing blended learning. The study identified various strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that educators encountered throughout the process. These discovery reflect the ongoing challenges that educational institutions in the region continue to face in adapting to blended learning environments. In the Philippines, specifically at Biñan City, various learning delivery modalities were implemented to address the community's geographical and socio-economic context. These modalities aimed to accommodate learners from diverse backgrounds by providing self-learning kits and modules for completion at home on a weekly basis, with the support of parents or guardians. However, challenges persist, including limited access to resources, difficulties in ensuring consistent communication, and varying levels of parental involvement, all of which continue to affect the effectiveness of the learning process. Teachers strive to maintain open communication channels with both learners and

parents to monitor progress and address individual learning needs, but overcoming these obstacles remains an ongoing task, ensuring a more inclusive and responsive educational environment. Locally, in Davao de Oro, teachers implementing blended learning face several challenges, particularly in striking a balance between the online and face-to-face components of their lessons. One major issue is the limited access to reliable internet and technology, which hinders both students' and teachers' ability to engage in online activities fully. Furthermore, teachers often struggle with ensuring the proper use of self-learning modules, as some students need more guidance and support, making independent learning difficult. Lastly, communication barriers between teachers, learners, and parents create difficulties in monitoring progress and addressing individual learning

needs, which in turn affect the overall effectiveness of the blended learning model in the region (Alamis et al., 2023). Accordingly, this qualitative study aims to explore how mathematics teachers perceive blended learning and its impact on their teaching practices, as well as its effect on learners' acquisition of knowledge. As part of this research, I explored the challenges that mathematics teachers encountered in implementing the blended learning system. I think that mathematics educators have different viewpoints on blended learning, with some seeing it as a chance to improve their teaching while others encounter difficulties in putting it into practice. Thus, it is within this premise that the study aims to investigate how mathematics teachers address issues and challenges in implementing the blended learning system in the new standard class setting.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study is to explore the relevance of the challenges in blended learning implementation with the experiences of mathematics teachers in the implementation of blended learning system, supplemented with the type of blended learning, and accompanied by the issues and challenges of blended learning system could bring out the lead experiences of mathematics teachers. In today's world, education is the key to economic survival. The part of blended learning system in the new normal class setting is increasing in prevalence and importance as educators understand its value and adjust to its influence. Accordingly, blended learning in teaching is the tool that will help teachers and learners, with the guidance of the

principal, to create new partnerships and unleash deeper learning. In addition, authentic learning through the use of blended learning system, allow learners to develop competencies, master content knowledge, and apply learning outcomes to contexts beyond the classroom. Therefore, blended learning system in teaching is a tool and resource working ubiquitously with the construction of knowledge and development of the new normal educational scheme. Specifically, the study aimed to draw significant information from the participants in terms of the lived experiences in their challenges in the implementation of blended learning approach as drawn from the findings of the study that will be conducted in Nabunturan East District, Davao de Oro Division.

1.2. Research Questions—This study was conducted to explore the challenges of mathematics teachers in the implementation of blended learning system. The following specific research questions set the direction of this study:

- (1) What are the challenges that mathematics teachers encounter in the blended learning implementation?
- (2) How do mathematics teachers cope with the challenges in the blended learning implemen-

tation?

(3) What insights did they gain from the study?

1.3. Significant of the Study—Mathematics Teachers

Mathematics teachers may benefit from this research through the efforts of the school principal to acknowledge their issues and to provide them with necessary support, resources, training, and programs, aided by the Department of Education, to help them tackle the obstacles associated with implementing blended learning.

School Principals

*1.4. Theoretical Lens—*This study is supported by the Social Learning Theory (SLT) by Bandura which is based on the idea that we learn from our interactions with others in a social context. Thus, the challenges in the implementation of blended learning system will be influential to the lead experiences of the mathematics teachers. Eventually, through the implementation of blended learning system, mathematics teachers will be able to assimilate, especially if their observational experiences are positive ones, the blended learning system in their teaching-learning process. This theory assumed to operate in the same way throughout life. Insofar as exposure to new influential, powerful models like the blended learning system, who control resources and may occur at life stage, new learning just like the implementation of blended learning system in teaching, is always possible. Social Learning Theory theorizes that people learn from one another through observation; imitation; and modeling. Based on these general principles, learning can occur without a change in behavior. In other words, behaviorists say that learning has to be represented by a permanent change in behavior; thus, blended learning system in teaching can be learned through observation. People can

Through this study, the school principals may be provided with an opportunity to address the difficulties of mathematics teachers with regard to the implementation of blended learning under the new normal class.

Department of Education

The Department of Education might use the findings from this study to help school principals tackle certain challenges related to the execution of the blended learning system in the Mathematics subject.

learn through observation which is known as observational learning. Thus, the implementation of blended learning system in teaching could be attributed to learning through observation and imitation of the skills of teachers, as well as to the support of the school leaders. People learn by watching what others do, and that human thought processes are central to understanding personality. This theory provides a framework for understanding, predicting and changing human behavior, which includes the development of the lead experiences of teachers that could lead to the full implementation of blended learning system. Another relevant theory for this study is Jerome Bruner's Constructivist Learning Theory (1973), which highlights that learning is less about passive information delivery and more about an active process where learners build their own knowledge based on what they already know. According to Constructivist Learning Theory, effective learning involves learners demonstrating their abilities by creating their own understanding while addressing real-world challenges. The constructivist approach advocates for instruction that prioritizes the learner since it is believed that students learn more effectively when they are encouraged to investigate and uncover informa-

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

tion independently. Technology should be integrated in ways that foster learner-centered teaching strategies within the classroom. Teachers play a crucial role in the development of ICT in the field of education. ICT integration illustrates a higher degree of embedding ICT tools in teaching-learning process. Likewise, dialogue simulations and role play exercises should be increasingly used by the teacher to promote communication skills. ICT tools should not only be used for every listening and speaking activity, but most importantly during the planning and design stage of a lesson the teacher should

give due consideration of when, when not and how to integrate. These provided safe spaces to negotiate understandings and for teachers to scaffold and support each other in shifting to blended learning. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the challenges that mathematics teachers encounter in the blended learning implementation; mathematics teachers cope with the challenges in blended learning implementation; and insights gained from the study.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presented the methodology, participants, data collection procedures, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and acquiring knowledge in this research required a structured design and careful implementation, which were discussed thoroughly in this chapter. The philosophical assumption served as a guiding framework in collecting, analyzing, and interpreting the data within the chosen field of study. It provided the foundation on which conclusions and decisions were later made. These philosophical assumptions took various forms and were described in detail. A good research endeavor started with the appropriate selection of topic, research problem, and the guiding paradigm. Patton (2020) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asked, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of this phenomenon for these people?” The objective of the study aligned with this definition, as it aimed to understand the lived experiences

of mathematics teachers in implementing the blended learning modality. The methodological framework of Abraham and Padmakumari (2025) aligns strongly with Giorgi's (2007) exhortation to transcend superficial layers: employing open-ended prompts to collect rich lived experiences, and a disciplined analytic process to distill psychological essences. It advised researchers to be prepared for an investigation that delved deeper and broader than what a surface-level description suggested. He emphasized that information should be seen as a superficial layer of a more profound experience.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption functioned as a lens in collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data within a specific research setting. It established the contextual foundation for the conclusions and decisions made in this study. These assumptions had different forms, each of which was explored in this section. The research process was grounded in choosing a relevant topic, defining the problem, and adhering to a suitable paradigm. The participants in the study were assumed to have answered the interview questions honestly and truthfully. Since it

was impractical to verify every single response through extensive validation, the sincerity of the participants was assumed. This assumption addressed the issue of reality in research. According to Creswell (2018), reality was understood as subjective and multifaceted, shaped by each participant's perspective. The philosophical beliefs underlying this study influence its design, methods, and the way findings are interpreted, guaranteeing a thorough and significant examination of the difficulties encountered by mathematics educators in applying blended learning.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—Methodology was described as a creative and adaptable strategy for grasping particular questions and topics, whereas methods represented the precise techniques utilized for data collection (Gerodias, 2013). This research examined the difficulties faced by mathematics educators in applying blended learning in the Nabunturan East District through In-Depth Interviews (IDI) and Focus Group Discussions (FGD). The researcher's commitment to uncovering deeper meanings behind the struggles encountered during blended learning implementation formed the foundation for conducting qualitative research. Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited by Gerodias (2013), highlighted that qualitative research aimed to uncover "meanings and motivations that underlie cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." Through phenomenology, the study sought to understand the lived experiences of

junior high school mathematics teachers, giving voice to their challenges and presenting them as meaningful themes, as described by David (2005). Phenomenological research operated under two primary assumptions: first, that experience was a valid and valuable source of knowledge; and second, that everyday life could reveal key insights when studied deeply. Becker (1992), as cited by Morrissey and Higgs (2006), supported the idea that personal experiences shaped behavior and were a legitimate source of understanding human phenomena. This view validated the study's reliance on the participants' firsthand accounts. Lastly, by applying the principles of phenomenology, especially focusing on the "what" and "how" of experience (Moustakas, 1995). I aimed to capture the dilemmas of junior high school teachers in a meaningful way and offer insights for future research and policy formulation.

2.3. Design and Procedure—

This study employed a phenomenological approach to explore specific experiences by examining their perception within a given context. In the realm of human experience, this often involves collecting in-depth information and insights through qualitative and inductive methods, including interviews, discussions, and participant observation, while presenting it from the viewpoint of the research participant(s). Phenomenology focuses on examining experiences from the individual's standpoint, setting aside preconceptions and conventional modes of understanding. The purpose of the phenomenological approach is to illuminate the specific, to identify phenomena through how they are perceived by the actors in a situation. In the human sphere, this normally translates into gathering 'deep' information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions and participant observation, and representing it from the perspective of the research participants (Forris, 2015). Phenomenology is a relevant philosophical methodology that I utilized to explore the dilemma of junior high school teachers in the implementation of the blended learning system.

2.4. Research Participants—This phenomenological study employed a small number of participants, which is typical for qualitative research. The sample size was sufficient to capture most, if not all, relevant perceptions, resulting in data saturation, which occurred when no new insights emerged from additional participants. Purposive sampling was used, selecting individuals based on specific criteria aligned with the study's objectives. Ten mathematics teachers from Nabunturan East, Davao de Oro Division participated, with seven engaging in in-depth interviews (IDI) and three in focus group discussions (FGD). The inclusion criteria required that participants were currently teaching mathematics in public schools within the division and had at least five years of experience. The data collected were used to identify emerging themes and patterns based on the participants' lived experiences. The purposive sampling method was adopted because participants were selected according to the study's purpose and criteria (Creswell, 2018), also referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations played a crucial role in the design and conduct of this research study. I took into account several ethical issues concerning the participants involved in the fieldwork. Ethics was regarded as one of the most vital aspects of the research process. I remained committed to upholding the integrity of the study by ensuring the promotion of its aims, delivering truthful and authentic knowledge, and avoiding errors.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—I held the responsibility of uncovering, transferring, and utilizing knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. I conducted interviews and guided participants throughout the process, interpreting their responses in light of relevant literature rather than personal bias. I correctly implemented qualitative methods, sought assistance from my adviser and research professionals, and demonstrated competence in conducting unbiased interviews, making observations, selecting relevant artifacts, and employing environmental triangulation and thematic content analysis. I ensured data collection through handwritten notes and audio recordings, and all recordings were transcribed verbatim. Data security and participant confidentiality were strictly upheld. Safeguarding mechanisms were communicated

to participants and approved by a research ethics board prior to the study. During data analysis, I interpreted the data from the participants' perspective by coding and theming, ensuring their voices were accurately represented. I also presented the related literature and the study's

findings in response to the research questions, using themes to illustrate how these questions were addressed. Future directions and policy implications were also highlighted to inform educational practices.

2.7. Data Collection—The data collection process followed several sequential steps. I secured an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges, a requirement for seeking approval from the Schools Division Superintendent. With this endorsement, I sent a request to the Schools Division Superintendent along with Chapters 1 and 2 of the thesis and the research instrument, clearly outlining the study's objectives and identifying the participants. Upon receiving approval, I informed the principals of the

selected schools by sending letters detailing the study. Consent was then obtained from the participants after they were formally oriented about the research process. The in-depth interviews were conducted using a structured interview guide. I then collected participants' profiles, took notes, and recorded conversations for transcription purposes. I listened attentively and responded appropriately during the interviews. The responses were transcribed precisely from the audio recordings. If the vernacular was used, the responses were translated into English.

2.8. Data Analysis—Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the data, guided by Creswell's model using the identification of themes approach. I familiarized myself with the data through repeated readings and initial note-taking. Coding was conducted to identify and label the significant characteristics of the data pertinent to the research questions. This process captured both surface meanings and underlying concepts. After coding, I collated re-

lated data extracts under each code. Themes were then developed to represent coherent and meaningful patterns. Each theme was reviewed for clarity and consistency with the research objectives. To enhance validity, Environmental Triangulation was used by altering environmental conditions such as time, location, and setting to determine if the findings remained consistent. If unchanged, validity was affirmed (David, 2015; Naeem Saira, 2019).

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The writing phase involved integrating analytical narratives and data excerpts to present a coherent and persuasive account, contextualized with relevant literature. The analytical framework was flexible, allowing for data analysis during or after collection. Data were sifted, sorted, and charted based on key themes and issues. The study followed

qualitative methods and adhered to a systematic approach for analysis, as outlined by O'Connor and Gibson (2003). I organized the data for ease of review, identified recurring words and concepts, and grouped them into codes and categories. Overarching themes were developed to give deeper meaning to the data, and related categories were consolidated under broader thematic concepts.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study)

Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness was crucial because the results and findings of the research depended on the process by which the study was conducted. The trustworthiness of a research study is crucial in evaluating its validity and worth. Due to the nature of qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes my study worthy of being read, shared, and taken pride in.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter systematically presented and critically interpreted the findings of the study through the lens of a qualitative research design. Anchored in the rich, descriptive data gathered from in-depth interviews, it explored the meanings and insights derived from the participants' lived experiences. The analysis focused on the emergent themes that surfaced from their narratives, offering a nuanced understanding of their perspectives in relation to the study's central phenomenon. To uphold ethical standards, brief participant profiles were included using pseudonyms to ensure confidentiality and anonymity.

3.1. Challenges that Mathematics Teachers Encounter In Blended Learning Implementation—Mathematics teachers face a range of challenges in implementing blended learning, especially in areas where technological access and limitations are prevalent. Inadequate internet connectivity, lack of devices, and limited technical support hinder both teaching and learning processes, making it difficult for teachers to deliver lessons effectively and for learners to access instructional materials consistently. These barriers are especially critical in math instruction, where real-time interaction and step-by-step problem solving are essential. The digital divide thus creates unequal learning experiences and impacts the overall quality of education delivered through blended modalities. In addition to technological issues, student motivation and participation often decline in blended setups, particularly when learners are left to work independently through modules or online platforms. Teachers also report being overwhelmed with increased workloads due to lesson preparation, assessment adjustments, and the need to constantly monitor learner progress through various channels. Many educators feel unprepared to balance in-person and online teaching requirements effectively, especially in subjects like mathematics that demand precision, engagement, and continuous feedback. These combined challenges highlight the need for systemic support in training, resources, and policy to enhance the successful implementation of blended learning in mathematics education.

3.1.1. Technological Access and Limitations—Technological access and limitations significantly affect the implementation of blended learning among mathematics teachers. Many educators face difficulties due to unreliable internet connectivity, lack of appropriate digital devices, and limited access to technical support. These constraints disrupt lesson delivery, hinder the use of interactive tools necessary for teaching complex mathematical concepts, and result in inconsistent learner engagement. In rural or under-resourced areas, these technological gaps widen the learning disparity among students and diminish the effectiveness of blended learning. Moreover, the lack of standardized digital infrastructure prevents mathematics teachers from fully integrating technology-based instructional strategies into their teaching practice. Teachers often spend additional time troubleshooting technical issues rather than focus-

ing on lesson facilitation, which leads to frustration and reduced instructional efficiency. These limitations not only affect teacher performance but also compromise learners' opportunity to benefit from meaningful and continuous math instruction. Addressing technological barriers is therefore essential to ensure the success of blended learning in mathematics education. The results of the study support Gilmour's (2020) findings, which identified technological access and limitations as major barriers in the effective implementation of blended learning. Similar to Gilmour's observations, the study revealed that many mathematics teachers struggle with insufficient digital resources, poor internet connectivity, and a lack of technical support. These issues hinder their ability to deliver consistent instruction and engage learners effectively in a blended setup. This alignment with Gilmour's study underscores the urgent need for improved technological infrastructure and professional development to support educators in blended learning environments. Osterlind (2019) and the California Office of Education (2020) both highlight that the rapid implementation of blended learning, mandated without sufficient preparation, intensified technological access and limitation issues among educators and learners. While blended learning offers benefits such as flexible scheduling and cost reduction, the lack of adequate digital infrastructure, reliable internet access, and proper technical support creates significant challenges. Teachers were expected to transition quickly to technology-based instruction without the necessary tools or training, resulting in inconsistent and often ineffective learning delivery. These findings emphasize that without addressing technological barriers, the advantages of blended learning cannot be fully realized in practice.

3.1.2. Learner Motivation and Participation—Maintaining learner motivation in a blended learning setting emerged as a persistent challenge among teachers. Mathematics,

in particular, requires active participation and immediate feedback, both of which are often absent in online or modular setups. Learners tend to disengage due to various reasons, ranging from internet access issues to emotional disconnect from peers and teachers. This disengagement leads to minimal participation, delayed submissions, and shallow learning outcomes. Teachers observed that learners struggled to work independently, especially in subjects like math that involve complex reasoning and step-by-step problem-solving. Without regular teacher scaffolding or peer support, learners often feel lost and disoriented. Compounding this issue is the minimal communication, where students fail to ask questions or seek clarification. This lack of feedback disrupts the learning process and limits learner growth and confidence. The findings of this study support the conclusions of Fauzi (2020), emphasizing that barriers to group task blended learning are closely linked to learner motivation and participation. Specifically, the study reveals that learners often struggle with understanding expectations, managing their time effectively, and engaging in meaningful interpersonal communication, factors that directly impact their motivation to participate. Likewise, teachers encountered challenges in clearly articulating expectations, providing prompt feedback, and nurturing constructive relationships with learners that significantly influence learner engagement. These difficulties often stem from limited time, inadequate skills in group collaboration, and minimal institutional support. Such findings support Moran's (2020) assertion that time pressures, lack of collaborative competence, insufficient guidance, and negative participant attitudes can undermine the success of group-based blended learning environments.

3.1.3. Teacher Preparedness and Workload—Blended learning demands a shift not only in tools but also in mindset, and many teachers were caught unprepared for the dig-

ital aspects of this transition. While some were quick to adapt, others reported struggling with platforms and tools that were previously unfamiliar to them. The lack of structured training before deployment meant that teachers had to learn on the fly, often with the help of colleagues or family members. This experience created an additional emotional burden that complicated their core teaching responsibilities. In addition to adapting to new teaching modalities, teachers faced a surge in their workloads due to the dual demands of online and modular instruction. Creating instructional videos, attending webinars, designing interactive content, and tracking individual student progress consumed time beyond regular hours. The emotional impact was also profound, as teachers experienced burnout, heightened anxiety, and a diminished sense of confidence in their ability to teach effectively. In the absence of structured support systems and ongoing professional development, the implementation of blended learning posed a serious threat to both the well-being and instructional performance of the educators responsible for its delivery. Upon reflecting on the lived experiences of mathematics teachers, it became clear to me as a researcher that the implementation of blended learning, while full of promise, carried significant complexities that deeply affected instructional delivery and teacher well-being. Their stories echoed not just logistical and technical challenges, but also emotional burdens and professional recalibrations that demanded resilience, creativity, and a

3.2. Mathematics Teachers Cope with the Challenges in Blended Learning Implementation—Despite the many difficulties encountered in blended learning, mathematics teachers have employed various coping strategies to adapt and sustain effective instruction. Teachers face numerous demands in their profession, making organizational stress an inevitable part of their

collaborative spirit. I realized that behind every modified lesson plan or adapted module was a teacher striving to preserve the integrity of learning despite limitations beyond their control. I understood the significance of being flexible and adaptable when facing challenges. Additionally, I recognized how crucial ongoing feedback and evaluation are in blended learning, as they foster trust and connection between teachers and allow me to pinpoint areas where students may require extra assistance. These insights not only deepened my understanding of the blended learning phenomenon but also reinforced the urgent need for holistic support systems that genuinely respond to the realities teachers face in the classroom and beyond. Additionally, blended learning has enabled teachers to support students who may have found traditional classroom environments challenging, giving them extra assistance and scaffolding through online activities and resources. The framework underscores the necessity of continuous training and assistance for educators to cultivate the skills and confidence required to seamlessly incorporate technology into their teaching. By equipping teachers with the appropriate resources and guidance, educational institutions can ensure that blended learning is applied in a manner that benefits students and improves teaching methodologies. This framework emphasizes the significance of investing in professional development for teachers to facilitate the effective integration of technology in mathematics education.

daily experiences. To cope effectively, they rely on Community Support and Collegial Collaboration, which provide a strong sense of belonging and shared responsibility. By working closely with fellow educators and receiving encouragement from school leaders, teachers can navigate challenges more easily and reduce feelings of isolation. This collaborative cul-

Fig. 3. Challenges that mathematics teachers encounter in the blended learning implementation

ture fosters professional growth and contributes to a more positive and resilient teaching environment. In addition, teachers employ Mental and Emotional Resilience Strategies to maintain their well-being and sustain their effectiveness in the classroom. Techniques such as self-reflection, mindfulness, and maintaining a positive mindset help them manage stress and remain focused on their teaching goals. Coupled with Time and Task Management practices such as prioritizing responsibilities, setting realistic goals, and organizing workloads, these strategies allow teachers to stay productive and avoid burnout. Together, these three themes form a comprehensive approach to managing organizational stress, resulting in enhanced teaching performance and increased overall job satisfaction. These coping mechanisms reflect not just technical adjustments but also the professional resilience and dedication of mathematics teachers to ensure learning continuity despite major challenges.

3.2.1. *Instructional Adaptation and Planning*—Teachers emphasized the need for dynamic lesson planning and material customization as a way to adapt to learners’ varying contexts and access levels. Developing simplified, bite-sized lessons and activity sheets allowed students to learn at their own pace, despite technological barriers. These resources not only provided flexibility but also ensured inclusivity for those with limited online access. The practice became a core strategy in addressing the equity gap inherent in blended setups. Through strategic intervention and pre-lesson scaffolding, teachers increased engagement while reducing student confusion. Instructional planning now included various examples, step-by-step problem-solving, and mastery checks that help both student and teacher monitor progress. The goal was to streamline content delivery while maintaining learning effectiveness. This method supported retention and made complex topics more accessible to students. Green and Peil (2019) emphasize that teachers, as effec-

tive educators in the new normal setting, must be capable of tackling new tasks and developing solutions in situations that require organizational learning and innovation. This concept is directly related to the theme of instructional adaptation and planning as supported by the findings of the study. Participants highlighted the necessity of adapting traditional teaching methods to suit blended learning environments, requiring teachers to develop and apply domain-specific teaching skills. These skills, acquired through instruction, training, and practice, were essential for creating flexible, meaningful, and accessible instructional materials that catered to diverse learner needs.

3.2.2. Emotional and Professional Resilience—Teachers displayed remarkable emotional resilience by adapting their attitudes and expectations during the shift to blended learning. Rather than resist change, many embraced it as an opportunity to grow and innovate their teaching. This growth mindset helped them navigate unfamiliar platforms and stressful conditions with greater confidence. Flexibility, humility, and openness to learning emerged as key traits that enabled teachers to cope effectively with the shifting demands. The cultivation of self-care practices and emotional boundaries played a vital role in sustaining teachers' mental health. Respondents highlighted the value of managing their reactions, regulating emotions, and setting realistic goals. Their ability to pause, reassess, and continue with renewed purpose served as a powerful buffer against burnout. Through reflection and self-awareness, teachers turned adversity into personal and professional transformation. Teachers' ability to adapt and use different strategies, like providing additional resources for learners who need them, demonstrates both emotional resilience in managing stress and professional resilience in their continued pursuit of effective teaching practices. Just as Khusuma (2020) suggests that mastery of knowledge and skills should be the focus, the study found that

teachers embraced personalized instruction, allowing learners to progress at their own pace and ensuring that learning was not solely dictated by time but by competency. Additionally, Means et al. (2019) emphasized that, to help all students meet high expectations, teachers must move beyond a traditional approach of providing the same inputs to each learner and instead focus on equity in both inputs and outcomes. This idea resonates with the essential theme of emotional and professional resilience identified in the study's findings. The study revealed that teachers faced numerous challenges in blended learning, including technological limitations and varying levels of learner engagement. However, teachers demonstrated resilience by adapting their instructional approaches to meet the diverse needs of their students, ensuring equitable learning opportunities for all. By applying a more nuanced instructional management style, educators in the study embraced flexibility and creativity, tailoring their efforts to support each learner's progress, which highlights both their emotional resilience in managing challenges and their professional resilience in adjusting to evolving teaching demands.

3.2.3. Collaboration and Support Systems—The implementation of blended learning required not just individual adaptation but collective effort among teachers. Many respondents described collaboration as key, whether through sharing instructional materials, exchanging digital tools, or offering emotional encouragement. The sense of mutual support helped teachers feel less isolated and more empowered to face blended learning's evolving demands. It was through peer dialogue that most found practical and morale-boosting solutions to daily classroom challenges. Beyond professional collaboration, teachers also leaned on personal support networks like family and trusted friends for technical or emotional guidance. This extended system provided essential reinforcement at a time when institutional support was limited.

Teachers who actively engaged in collaborative practices both formal (e.g., webinars, mentoring) and informal (e.g., daily check-ins) showed better adjustment and resilience. Strengthening collegial bonds not only reduced stress but fostered a culture of adaptability and shared success. Awaad (2019) highlighted that teachers measure progress based on the attainment of competencies, adjusting their approach to meet learners at various points along their individual learning journeys, rather than following rigid, one-size-fits-all schedules or instructional sequences. This perspective emphasizes the importance of collaboration and support systems in education, as teachers must actively engage with learners, understanding their unique strengths, skills, and needs. By valuing each learner, including those with diverse abilities and exceptionalities, educators are better equipped to personalize their instruction and create a supportive learning environment. This collaborative approach acknowledges that effective teaching goes beyond the curriculum and involves recognizing and responding to the individual needs of students, ensuring that all learners receive the necessary support to succeed. Based on the figure 4 presented, three key themes emerged from the participants' responses: instructional adaptation and planning, emotional and professional resilience, and collaboration and support systems. The findings of the study reveal that instructional adaptation and planning are crucial for effective teaching in the blended learning environment. Teachers emphasized the need to adjust to traditional teaching methods to suit both online and offline contexts, ensuring that learning materials are accessible and engaging for all learners. This theme highlights the importance of continuously adapting instructional strategies to meet the diverse needs of students while maintaining the rigor and quality of the learning experience. Moreover, the study demonstrated the significant role of emotional and professional resilience in navigating the challenges of blended learning. Teachers exhibited resilience by maintaining high expectations and adapting to the demands of new teaching methods, even in the face of technological barriers and learner disengagement. This resilience is further supported by the theme of collaboration and support systems, as teachers recognized the need for teamwork and the creation of supportive networks to enhance both their own professional growth and the success of their learners. Collaboration among educators, as well as support from families and peers, was essential for overcoming obstacles and fostering an environment where all learners could thrive. Through the views and sentiments shared by the participants, I came to realize that coping with the challenges of blended learning is not merely about acquiring new strategies, but about nurturing a mindset of persistence, adaptability, and purpose. I was particularly struck by how teachers embraced change and not by resisting it, but by reshaping their approaches with compassion, creativity, and collective support. Their ability to manage stress while still prioritizing student learning made me appreciate the unseen emotional labor teachers carry each day. This deepened my belief that fostering a supportive, collaborative environment is crucial in sustaining teacher well-being and ensuring the success of blended learning practices. Understanding how teachers transformed adversity into action affirmed for me that resilience in education is both a personal and communal journey. Their stories revealed that behind every successful adaptation lies a network of shared experiences, silent sacrifices, and continuous learning. As a researcher, I was reminded that effective teaching in blended learning environments does not rest solely on resources or platforms, but on the human capacity to connect, adjust, and persevere. This understanding left me with a profound respect for educators who rise above limitations not just to teach, but to uplift and empower their learners.. Although there are obstacles to im-

Fig. 4. Mathematics Teachers cope with the challenges in blended learning implementation

plementing blended learning, such as technical difficulties and ensuring fairness, I believe that the advantages significantly outweigh the disadvantages. By adopting blended learning, teach-

ers have been able to foster a more dynamic, inclusive, and effective educational setting for students.

3.3. Insights Gained in the Study—The study revealed that teamwork and collaboration significantly help teachers manage organizational stress in a blended learning environment. Teachers found that sharing responsibilities, communicating openly, and working towards common goals not only reduced individual workloads but also fostered a strong sense of unity and mutual support. This collective effort provided both emotional and practical relief, allowing teachers to cope more effectively with academic demands and unexpected challenges. Through consistent collaboration, teachers created a culture of empathy and shared success, which proved vital in sustaining their professional resilience. Additionally, themes of adaptability and digital innovation were central to

teachers' positive transition into blended learning. Educators learned to embrace change with optimism, using flexibility as a tool to manage uncertainty and develop professionally. Exposure to new technologies enhanced their teaching methods, allowing for personalized and engaging instruction that catered to students' varied needs. This experience not only improved instructional delivery but also empowered teachers to become lifelong learners and innovators, ready to navigate the evolving educational landscape with confidence and creativity. The findings of this study align closely with Bandura's Social Learning Theory, as teachers navigated the blended learning system through observation, modeling, and interaction within their educational communities. Many educators in the

study expressed that their adaptability and confidence in using digital tools improved as they learned from their colleagues' strategies, responses, and classroom practices. This form of observational learning enabled them to assimilate blended learning methods effectively, especially when guided by supportive peers and school leaders who served as role models. The challenges and successes encountered became influential experiences, reinforcing the idea that learning in a social context especially through shared professional experiences, can drive lasting instructional transformation. Moreover, the findings also reflect Bruner's Constructivist Learning Theory, emphasizing the active role of teachers in constructing their professional knowledge and teaching strategies within the blended learning environment. Teachers in the study actively explored new technologies, adapted lesson designs, and reflected on their practice, demonstrating the constructivist belief that meaningful learning arises through real-world problem solving. The integration of ICT tools empowered educators to create learner-centered, flexible instruction while simultaneously constructing their own understanding of effective pedagogy in the digital age. These experiences affirm that when teachers are placed in environments that encourage exploration and collaboration, they become agents of innovation, shaping their teaching practices through continuous, self-directed learning.

3.3.1. Adaptability and Positive Outlook—A significant insight shared by many teachers was the realization that flexibility and adaptability are not just survival strategies, but also essential tools for professional success. The sudden shift to blended learning demanded rapid innovation and tolerance for uncertainty. Teachers who reframed challenges as learning opportunities found themselves better equipped to adapt and thrive. Their positive mindset became a cornerstone in managing stress and building long-term capacity. Reflective practices such

as pausing, reassessing, and redirecting energy helped educators convert stressful moments into growth experiences. Teachers noted that their ability to cope improved when they allowed themselves room to learn, make mistakes, and recalibrate without guilt. The discipline to maintain a hopeful and proactive outlook enabled them to rise above the pressure of continuous change. In the process, many discovered not only better stress responses but a renewed sense of purpose in their profession. Yazon (2020) emphasized that teaching attitudes encompass personal traits and behavioral patterns that enable educators to transition effectively into new modes of teaching and learning. This assertion aligns closely with the study's theme of adaptability and positive outlook, as participants demonstrated a strong willingness to embrace change and explore innovative strategies during the shift to blended learning. Teachers who approached this transition with optimism and openness were more likely to adapt their instructional methods, creating meaningful and engaging experiences for their learners. In connection with the findings, educators who viewed challenges as learning opportunities were able to foster supportive environments where learners could engage comfortably, often comparing their strategies to natural conversations with peers. As Yazon suggests, such personal engagement and flexibility help learners grasp concepts more effectively, which was mirrored in the participants' reflections about student-centered and relational approaches. Ultimately, the ability to adapt with a positive mindset empowered teachers to lead lessons that were both effective and responsive to learners' evolving needs. Moreover, Abdalhadi (2019) highlighted the importance of teachers adopting a facilitative attitude, guiding learners to construct meaning in their own way while ensuring conceptual understanding aligns with learning objectives. This perspective strongly resonates with the study's theme of adaptability and positive

outlook, as participants reflected on their shift from teacher-centered approaches to more flexible, learner-driven strategies during blended learning. Teachers adapted by embracing roles as facilitators, allowing students to engage with content at their own pace while creatively adjusting their methods to maintain clarity and depth of instruction. This positive and adaptive mindset empowered educators to support diverse learning styles and needs, demonstrating how openness to evolving roles enhanced both teaching effectiveness and learner outcomes in the blended setting.

3.3.2. Value of Team Work and Shared Responsibility—One of the key insights drawn from the teachers' reflections was the power of collaboration in mitigating organizational stress. They learned that tackling work-related pressures does not have to be an isolated effort. Shared goals, task distribution, and group problem-solving not only improved workflow but also created a collective sense of achievement. Teachers found that stress became more manageable when they were emotionally and practically supported by their peers. The act of working together cultivated a culture of empathy and unity. Teachers recognized that openly communicating about their struggles invited solutions and emotional encouragement. By depending on one another, they were able to create a supportive environment that helped them cope with pressures from administrative tasks, academic deliverables, and sudden transitions. This interdependence proved to be both a coping strategy and a long-term resilience framework.

3.3.3. Digital Empowerment and Innovation—One of the most transformative lessons that emerged was the enhancement of teachers' digital literacy. Respondents repeatedly mentioned that using various platforms pushed them beyond their traditional pedagogical boundaries. Through exposure to new technologies and online teaching tools, teachers discovered how to better integrate multimedia, online assessments,

and interactive content. These insights not only expanded their technical skill sets but also improved instructional effectiveness. Blended learning taught teachers to become educational innovators. They experimented with tools like ThatQuiz, ZipGrade, and online videos, finding more engaging and efficient ways to deliver complex concepts. This empowered them to tailor content to individual student needs while embracing lifelong learning. Ultimately, their ability to adapt creatively and intelligently to the demands of a digital classroom environment proved to be a key factor in managing stress and thriving professionally. Based on the figure 5 presented, three themes emerged from the responses of the participants with regards to insights gain from the study which were: adaptability and positive outlook, value of team work and shared responsibility, and digital empowerment and innovation. The findings of the study highlight the importance of adaptability and a positive outlook as vital traits that helped teachers thrive in the blended learning environment. Faced with uncertainty and rapid change, many educators chose to view challenges as opportunities for growth rather than setbacks. Their ability to remain flexible, reassess strategies, and maintain a hopeful mindset allowed them to develop resilience and sustain motivation. This optimistic approach not only reduced stress but also reignited their passion for teaching. Another key insight drawn from the study is the value of teamwork and shared responsibility, which proved crucial in managing organizational pressures. Teachers found that collaborating with colleagues, sharing tasks, and exchanging strategies helped reduce their workload and improve overall productivity. The culture of mutual support fostered trust, emotional safety, and unity within school communities. Through open communication and cooperation, teachers were better equipped to handle the demands of blended learning. Lastly, the study emphasized the power of digital empowerment and

Fig. 5. The Insights gained in the study

innovation in transforming teaching practices. Exposure to various educational technologies enabled teachers to integrate multimedia tools, digital assessments, and interactive content into their instruction. This not only increased learner engagement but also enhanced the teachers' confidence and effectiveness. Embracing digital tools encouraged educators to become innovators in their classrooms, reinforcing their capacity to navigate modern educational landscapes successfully. As mathematics educators, the views and insights regarding blended learning

are diverse. Even with its challenges, teachers come to value the adaptability and individualized approach that blended learning provides. By utilizing online tools and resources, various learning preferences and abilities can be addressed, offering a more customized educational experience for students. It is also noticed that blended learning can enhance student participation and enthusiasm, especially when interactive and multimedia content is employed to explain intricate mathematical ideas.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This study presents a multi-faceted understanding of the lived experiences of mathematics teachers as they navigate the complex realities of implementing blended learning in public secondary schools. Grounded in their voices, the findings reveal how deeply interconnected factors such as technological access, learner engagement, and institutional preparedness shape the effectiveness of blended instruction. The teachers' coping strategies ranging from instructional adaptations to emotional resilience and collaborative support, highlight their agency and adaptability amidst

systemic constraints. These insights offer a critical foundation for designing more responsive interventions, rethinking leadership practices, and informing policy directions that prioritize both instructional quality and teacher well-being in the evolving landscape of blended education.

4.1. Findings—The result of the study revealed three core challenges faced by mathematics teachers: technological access and limitations, learner motivation and participation, and teacher preparedness and workload. These challenges imply that future strategies may focus on addressing the digital divide, especially in under-resourced areas where poor connectivity and limited devices hinder instruction. Strengthening school-based digital infrastructure and providing learners and teachers with functional and accessible technological tools may improve equity in blended learning delivery. Furthermore, the issue of low learner motivation implies that instructional models may incorporate gamified content, interactive lessons, and mentorship initiatives to foster engagement. Since mathematics demands active feedback and step-by-step guidance, structured online routines and personalized learning pathways may support learners more effectively. The concern about preparedness and workload indicates that support systems such as time-saving assessment tools, collaborative lesson planning, and regular coaching sessions may be institutionalized to lessen the burden on teachers and promote professional efficiency. In response to the challenges they face, teachers developed adaptive strategies categorized under instructional adaptation and planning, emotional and professional resilience, and collaboration and support systems. The implication of these coping mechanisms is that continuous professional development programs may focus not only on content delivery but also on planning inclusive materials tailored to learners' technological and cognitive contexts. As teachers demonstrated flexibility by modifying content into more accessible, modular forms, future training may promote differentiated instruction and microlearning de-

sign. Emotional and professional resilience highlighted the importance of self-care practices and reflective teaching. Schools may consider embedding mental wellness initiatives and time management support into teacher development agendas. Lastly, the strong reliance on collegial networks shows that peer mentoring, communities of practice, and collaborative problem-solving initiatives may be formalized and supported by school leaders to build a sustainable culture of support in times of educational transitions. Teachers shared meaningful reflections that revealed three core themes shaping their experiences: adaptability and a positive outlook, a strong sense of teamwork and shared responsibility, and a growing confidence in digital empowerment and innovation. These insights illustrate how the success of blended learning is deeply influenced by environments that foster professional agency, openness to experimentation, and reflective teaching practices. The emphasis on collaboration points to the importance of collective efforts such as co-planning, peer observation, and shared instructional responsibilities in navigating blended modalities. Likewise, the recognition of digital empowerment highlights a shift in how teachers engage with technology, not just as a tool for access, but as a means to transform pedagogy and enrich the learning experience.

4.2. Implications—The findings of this study suggest that while blended learning offers potential advantages in enhancing instructional delivery, its implementation is hindered by systemic barriers, particularly for mathematics teachers. The lack of access to stable internet, limited availability of learning devices, and insufficient digital infrastructure continue to hinder the quality and equity of instruction. These technological constraints not

only limit the effectiveness of teaching strategies but also reinforce educational inequality among students from diverse socio-economic backgrounds. Technological access emerged as a critical barrier to the effective implementation of blended learning, particularly among mathematics teachers who require real-time instructional interaction and feedback mechanisms. Participants consistently cited poor internet connectivity, limited availability of devices, and the absence of technical support as persistent obstacles that disrupted the teaching flow and learner engagement. These constraints disproportionately affected learners from low-resource communities, widening the digital divide and impeding equitable access to education. The limitations not only undermined teachers' ability to deliver instructional content efficiently but also intensified their workload, as more time was spent troubleshooting rather than facilitating learning. These findings highlight that unless technological infrastructure and digital support systems are prioritized, mathematics instruction under blended learning will remain fragmented and inconsistent. A recurring theme among participants was the diminished learner motivation and participation in blended learning environments. Teachers reported that learners often displayed disengagement, missed deadlines, and lacked initiative, particularly when left to navigate modular or asynchronous online tasks independently. In mathematics, a subject that relies heavily on sequential understanding and guided practice, this lack of active involvement led to superficial learning and frequent misunderstandings. Participants noted that the emotional distance and reduced peer interaction in blended settings further alienated students, limiting collaborative learning opportunities. These experiences suggest that blended learning requires not only technological readiness but also effective emotional and social engagement strategies to maintain learner motivation, especially in subjects with abstract and complex content, such as mathematics. The transition to blended learning significantly reshaped the professional responsibilities of mathematics teachers, intensifying their workload while demanding new technical competencies. Many participants admitted to initially feeling overwhelmed by the simultaneous expectations of designing digital content, facilitating both face-to-face and remote sessions, and ensuring ongoing learner assessment. The absence of pre-implementation training exacerbated this challenge, forcing educators to rely on trial-and-error approaches or informal peer support. The pressure to produce customized materials, often without institutional backing, contributed to burnout and diminished teaching efficacy. These insights underscore the importance of structured capacity-building programs and institutional recognition of the increased workload borne by educators navigating the blended learning modality. Mathematics teachers demonstrated strategic adaptability by redesigning their instructional plans to suit the diverse technological contexts and learning needs of students. Participants described modifying lessons into simplified formats, breaking down complex topics into manageable learning segments, and integrating alternative delivery tools such as printed learning activity sheets and offline tasks. This proactive planning enabled them to sustain learning continuity even in areas with limited connectivity. The shift towards more learner-friendly pacing, scaffolded instruction, and customized assessment signified a deep pedagogical shift aimed at inclusivity. Such adaptations reflect not only technical responses but also a pedagogical transformation driven by the imperative to make mathematics more accessible and meaningful in hybrid contexts. The study disclosed that emotional resilience played a central role in how teachers navigated the uncertainties and pressures of blended teaching. Many respondents shared how maintaining a growth mindset, practicing patience, and adjusting their expect-

tations allowed them to remain composed and responsive amidst stress. The ability to self-reflect, acknowledge limitations, and seek small successes in day-to-day teaching helped teachers preserve their morale. Professionally, they embraced continuous learning, engaged with evolving digital tools, and accepted the fluid nature of their roles. These responses indicate that psychological flexibility and resilience are just as crucial as technical skills in sustaining teacher efficacy during instructional transitions. A strong sense of community among teachers was highlighted as a significant coping mechanism in the implementation of blended learning. Collegial collaboration, whether through informal exchanges, shared resources, or team discussions, provided moral support and practical solutions to common challenges. Participants valued peer mentoring and administrative encouragement, noting that these networks reduced feelings of isolation and fostered a collective problem-solving culture. Support systems also included emotional validation, with teachers checking in on one another's well-being amid heightened professional demands. These findings suggest that institutionalizing professional learning communities and collaborative planning time may strengthen not only instructional quality but also teacher well-being and retention. The theme of adaptability and positive outlook reflects teachers' evolving mindsets in embracing the challenges posed by blended learning. Their willingness to adjust instructional strategies, adopt new tools, and remain flexible amidst uncertainty suggests that professional resilience plays a crucial role in sustaining effective teaching. This implies that adaptability is not merely a reactive skill but a proactive stance that shapes how educators respond to rapid changes in educational delivery. From this lens, cultivating a culture that values continuous learning and mindset development becomes essential in preparing teachers to thrive in dynamic teaching environments. The findings reinforce that emotional agility and optimism can empower educators to turn challenges into opportunities for growth and pedagogical creativity. The prominence of teamwork and shared responsibility as a theme underscores the collective nature of effective blended learning implementation. Teachers expressed that collaboration among colleagues, instructional co-planning, and peer support were not only helpful but often essential in managing workload and overcoming instructional barriers. This insight suggests that individual teacher performance is deeply interconnected with collegial networks and school culture. When educators are given structured time and space to collaborate, exchange feedback, and co-develop materials, the implementation of blended learning becomes more sustainable and responsive to both teacher and learner needs. Therefore, shared responsibility emerges not only as a strategy for survival but also as a catalyst for professional enrichment and instructional coherence. Digital empowerment and innovation emerged as a transformative insight from teachers who, over time, became more confident and experimental in using technology to enhance their teaching practices. Initially marked by apprehension, their journey into digital learning tools evolved into a space for pedagogical reinvention, enabling more interactive, accessible, and data-informed teaching approaches. This implies that when teachers are provided the opportunity to explore digital tools in meaningful ways, they can shift from passive users to empowered designers of learning. Moreover, their growing familiarity with digital platforms not only improved content delivery but also allowed them to personalize instruction and monitor student progress more effectively. This insight calls attention to the importance of fostering digital fluency as an evolving competency that supports both innovation and equity in education. From my perspective as the researcher, the themes across all research questions reveal

how deeply rooted the challenges, coping strategies, and insights of mathematics teachers are in their everyday realities. The issues of limited technology, learner disengagement, and overwhelming workloads highlight the urgent need for practical, grounded support in blended learning contexts. I found it particularly meaningful how teachers relied on collaboration, adaptability, and digital exploration to sustain their teaching amidst uncertainty. These lived experiences reaffirmed my understanding that empowering teachers through shared responsibility, emotional resilience, and continuous professional growth is essential to making blended learning both sustainable and transformative.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, the following future directions are proposed to guide significant individuals in enhancing the implementation and sustainability of blended learning approaches. These directions are intended to ensure that the research insights are meaningfully translated into practice.

Mathematics Teachers

Mathematics teachers may engage in ongoing, subject-specific professional development centered on digital pedagogy, assessment strategies, and learner interaction techniques. Establishing systems such as instructional coaching, peer collaboration sessions, and onboarding workshops for technology use may enhance instructional quality. Teachers might also consider developing localized instructional materials that reflect the specific needs and contexts of their learners.

All Teachers

Educators across various disciplines may find value in joining structured communities of practice where they can co-develop lesson plans, share innovations, and access emotional and professional support. Training on blended learning practices may be adapted to accommodate diverse teaching styles and student needs. Institutional efforts to promote teacher wellness,

such as access to mental health resources and equitable workload distribution may also contribute to more effective and sustainable teaching environments.

Learners

Learners may benefit from focused digital literacy training and structured orientation sessions to support their effective use of self-learning modules. Designing personalized and interactive content could foster greater self-regulation, intrinsic motivation, and a sense of ownership over learning. The integration of peer tutoring and guided learning circles may also help strengthen accountability, encourage collaboration, and create a more supportive learning environment.

School Administrators

School leaders may begin by conducting needs assessments and readiness evaluations before implementing blended learning initiatives. Leadership development programs might incorporate digital planning and adaptive supervision. Additionally, forming partnerships with local stakeholders can help tailor training programs to the specific needs of schools and communities.

DepEd Officials

The Department of Education may consider enhancing monitoring and evaluation systems to track the effectiveness and equity of blended learning initiatives. Investing in community-level digital infrastructure, teacher training programs, and scalable support mechanisms may help build the capacity needed for inclusive learning. Flexible policy frameworks that account for the varying readiness and resources across regions could further support successful implementation.

Policy Makers

Policy makers may consider establishing long-term, inclusive frameworks that position blended learning as a regular modality within the education system. Policies might emphasize equitable access to technology, professional de-

velopment requirements, integration of digital curriculum, and performance-based incentives for educators. Collaboration between education sectors, ICT agencies, and local governments may be instrumental in addressing digital inequality and ensuring systemic support.

Future Researchers

Future research may focus on conducting comparative and longitudinal studies across regions, grade levels, and subject areas to deepen understanding of blended learning. Investigating its long-term effects on student outcomes, instructional practices, and learner retention could yield valuable insights.

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